

Kinetics of Oxidation of α -Hydroxy Acids by Acid Dichromate

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Acid dichromate oxidation of α -hydroxy acids, such as mandelic, lactic, benzoic and benzylphenylglycolic acids, shows that the reaction is first order with respect to both [oxidant] and [substrate]. The reaction is acid catalysed and the order with respect to $[H^+]$ is unity. Both $HCrO_4^-$ and $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ seem to participate in the reaction. Consistent with the result of oxidation and product analysis, a reaction path involving the formation of cyclic-chromate ester which decomposes in the rate limiting step by oxidative decarboxylation, has been suggested. The oxidation has been shown to proceed by two-electron transfer.

A review of literature shows that kinetics of oxidation of α -hydroxy acids by different metal ions¹⁻⁵ have been studied by a number of workers. As a part of our programme on the acid dichromate oxidation of organic compounds containing active functions, the present paper describes the kinetics of oxidation of α -hydroxy acids.

Experimental

Cr^{VI} solution was prepared from AnalaR potassium dichromate. Mandelic acid (MA), benzoic acid (BA) and lactic acid (LA) were of Fluka. Benzylphenylglycolic acid (BPGA) was prepared and purified by standard procedure⁶. Glacial acetic acid (G. R., S. Merck) was used as solvent. Demineralised water was used for preparing different compositions of solvent mixture. All other chemicals used were either AnalaR or G.R. grade.

Kinetic measurement : Kinetic experiments were initiated by mixing equal volumes of two solutions (both being pre-equilibrated at the reaction temperature), one containing dichromate solution and the other organic substrate dissolved in acetic acid. The course of the reaction was followed by the method described in our earlier paper⁷. The duplicate rate measurements were reproducible to $\pm 3\%$.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of the reaction was found by allowing a known excess of acid dichromate solution to react with

the substrate for 48 h in an atmosphere of nitrogen. A blank experiment was also simultaneously run to take into account the consumption of Cr^{VI} by the solvent. Unused Cr^{VI} was determined. Stoichiometric studies between Cr^{VI} and α -hydroxy acids indicate 1 : 3 mole-ratio. The product from benzoic acid was benzophenone which was isolated and characterised by its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (m.p. 239°) and from its ir spectra. The product from mandelic acid was detected to be benzaldehyde by spot test⁸. In consideration of the stoichiometry and product analysis, the overall reaction for mandelic acid oxidation may be represented by the following equation,

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of mandelic acid by acid dichromate has been studied in detail in acetic acid-water mixture of definite composition (v/v) at constant acidity and ionic strength.

Effect of varying [substrate] and [oxidant] : The order with respect to the concentration of Cr^{VI} and the concentration of mandelic acid was observed to be one each (Table 1). Although, the rate of disappearance of Cr^{VI} follows a first order rate law, the rate constants show a decreasing trend with increase in initial concentration of Cr^{VI} . This type of behaviour is, however, not uncommon with Cr^{VI}

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CHANGING [SUBSTRATE] AND [OXIDANT]

$[H_2SO_4] = 0.5 M, \mu = 0.505 M,$
 $Temp. = 35^\circ, HOAc-H_2O = 1:1 (v/v)$

$[Cr^{VI}]$ $\times 10^3 M$	$[MA]$ $\times 10^3 M$	k_1 $\times 10^3 s^{-1}$	$[HCrO_4^-]$ $\times 10^3 M$	$k_1[Cr^{VI}] \times 10^6 s^{-1}$ $[HCrO_4^-]$
1.67	1.0	10.97	1.645	11.1
1.43	1.0	12.09	1.236	13.9
1.25	1.0	13.17	1.1	14.9
1.0	1.0	14.21	0.9	15.5
0.91	1.0	14.75	0.825	16.2
1.0	1.25	17.75	—	—
1.0	0.83	12.08	—	—
1.0	0.71	10.14	—	—

oxidations⁹. The decreasing trend in the rate constant may be due to the hydrolytic equilibrium between $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ and $HCrO_4^-$. In view of this, $[HCrO_4^-]$ has been calculated for each initial concentration of Cr^{VI} using value¹⁰ of $K_b = 1.6 \times 10^{-3}$ at 35° . The ratios between the observed rate and $[HCrO_4^-]$ do not show constancy indicating that $HCrO_4^-$ is not the only oxidising species responsible for this oxidation. The observed data fit into the expression,

$$\frac{-d[Cr^{VI}]}{dt} = a [HCrO_4^-] + b [HCrO_4^-]^2$$

Plot of $rate/[HCrO_4^-]$ vs $[HCrO_4^-]$ gives a straight line from which the values of constants 'a' and 'b' are computed to be 20.5×10^{-4} and 6.56×10^{-1} , respectively. This is indicative of the participation of both $HCrO_4^-$ and $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ in the oxidation process. Similar views have also been expressed in the oxidation of *p*-methoxyacetophenone¹¹ and malonic acid¹² by Cr^{VI} . The plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[MA]$ at 35° is linear with no intercept on $1/k_{obs}$ axis. This indicates the absence of a preformed complex or a complex whose formation constant is too low to be kinetically determined.

Acid dependence : The oxidation of mandelic acid by Cr^{VI} has also been studied at various concentrations of sulphuric acid and potassium sulphate (Tables 2 and 3). The reaction is found to be acid catalysed. Plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [H_2SO_4]$ is linear and the order of the reaction with respect to the acid is one. The rate of the reaction is not appreciably affected by increasing the concentration of SO_4^{2-} . This shows that H^+ is only responsible for rate increase when sulphuric acid concentration is increased. The anions, like ClO_4^- and HSO_4^- increase the tendency of Cr^{VI} species to accept electrons from a reducing agent. Since ClO_4^- is more electron withdrawing than HSO_4^- , the rate of oxidation of mandelic acid in $HClO_4$ medium is found to be higher than that in sulphuric acid medium (Table 4).

Effect of solvent-composition on rate : The rate of the reaction has been observed to increase with increasing acetic acid content in solvent mixture

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF $[H_2SO_4]$ AND SOLVENT COMPOSITION

$[MA] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M, [Cr^{VI}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M, Temp. = 35^\circ$

$[H_2SO_4]$ M	HOAc %	k_1 $\times 10^3 dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$
0.4	50	1.24
0.5	50	1.42
0.65	50	1.75
0.8	50	2.29
0.5	40	0.91
0.5	60	2.24
0.5	70	3.47
0.5	80	5.23

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF $[Mn^{II}]$, IONIC STRENGTH AND $[K_2SO_4]$

$[Cr^{VI}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M, [MA] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M, [H_2SO_4] = 0.5 M,$
 $Temp = 35^\circ, HOAc-H_2O = 1:1 (v/v)$

$[Mn^{II}]$ $\times 10^3 M$	k_1 $\times 10^3 dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$	μ M	k_1 $\times 10^3 dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$	$[K_2SO_4]$ $\times 10^3 M$	k_1 $\times 10^3 dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$
0.0	1.42	0.505	1.42	0.0	1.42
0.5	1.21	0.6	1.31	1.5	1.41
0.67	1.12	0.7	1.25	2.0	1.40
1.0	1.03	0.8	1.12	2.5	1.38
2.0	0.86	0.9	0.94	3.0	1.35

(Table 2). The plot of $\log k$ vs reciprocal of dielectric constant has been observed to be linear with a positive slope indicating the possibility of ion-ion interaction or ion-dipole interaction. First order dependence on $[H_2SO_4]$ does not show the involvement of a positively charged Cr^{VI} species. Hence, the possibility of the reaction between a positively charged Cr^{VI} species and mandelic acid may be ruled out under the experimental conditions of present reaction. An increase in ionic strength by adding potassium hydrogen sulphate decreases the rate (Table 3). The concentrations of ions being much above the limit at which Debye-Hückel relationship is valid, the effect of ionic strength on rate suggests qualitatively the interaction between two oppositely charged reacting species. Since the possibility of participation of positively charged Cr^{VI} species has been ruled out, the interaction probably takes place between H^+ and a negative ion. This assumption is not unreasonable as the absence of mineral acid considerably retards the rate of the reaction.

Nature of chromium (VI) species : It is not easy to decide the exact molecular identity of Cr^{VI} species present in the solution, since it is involved in a series of protolytic and hydrolytic equilibria, e.g.

In addition to the above, species $HCrO_4^-$ and $HCrO_4^+$ are known to combine with HSO_4^- in

sulphuric acid to form Cr^{VI} species¹²⁻¹⁶, CrSO_4^{2-} and HCrO_3 , HSO_4^- . Since the reaction has been carried out in acetic acid medium, Cr^{VI} is also expected to exist in the form of an acetyl chromate ion $\text{AcO}(\text{CrO}_3)^-$. The details of present oxidation being carried out in 0.5 M sulphuric acid, Cr^{VI} species involved in the reaction seem to be HCrO_4^- and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$.

Effect of addition of Mn^{II} ion: The rate data for the effect of adding Mn^{II} ion have been recorded in Table 3. The rate decreases by increas-

tion reaction. If the reaction proceeds by either (i) and (ii), a free radical would be generated in the rate determining step or later if it follows the path (iii). The formation of free radical was neither indicated in the initial stage of the reaction nor at the later stage of the reaction by addition of acrylonitrile or mercuric chloride. Hence, reduction of Cr^{VI} does not pass through the paths (i), (ii) or (iii). It is therefore reasonable to assume that the reaction of acid dichromate with mandelic acid proceeds through path (iv) and Cr^{VI} essentially behaves as a two-electron oxidant.

TABLE 4—RATE CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

$[\text{Cr}^{VI}] = 1.10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Sub}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Acid}] = 0.5 \text{ M}$,
 $\mu = 0.505 \text{ M}$, $\text{HOAc-H}_2\text{O} = 1:1 \text{ (v/v)}$

Substrate	$k_2 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$				ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔF^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
	35°	40°	45°	50°			
BPGA in H_2SO_4	6.35	9.81	15.56	24.12	73.6	83	31
BA in H_2SO_4	3.48	5.05	7.07	11.15	60.4	84.6	78.5
MA in H_2SO_4	1.42	2.35	3.78	5.85	74.1	86.8	41.2
LA in H_2SO_4	0.48	0.72	0.92	1.27	50.2	89.7	128.2
MA in HClO_4	2.26	3.52	5.67	8.77	72.4	85.7	43.2

ing the concentration of Mn^{II} . This is indicative of the formation of some lower valent chromium species^{17,18}. Reduction of rate by addition of Mn^{II} is expected if it catalyses the disproportionation of intermediate valency states of chromium and suggests that Cr^{IV} is probably involved as intermediate.

Structure-reactivity relation: The reactivity of substituted α -hydroxy acids conforms to the following order (Table 4), $\text{BPGA} > \text{BA} > \text{MA} > \text{LA}$.

A common mechanism for the oxidation of substituted α -hydroxy acids may be envisaged as the free energy of activation values are of same order of magnitude. The negative values of entropy of activation suggest rigid transition state. The above order of reactivity indicates that the bulk of the group controls the rate of oxidation.

Mechanism: Reduction of Cr^{VI} to Cr^{III} by organic substrates is known to occur in one-step by transfer of three electrons or by (i) stepwise one-electron involvement, (ii) one-electron transfer in initial step followed by a two-electron transfer in another step, (iii) initial two-electron transfer followed by one-electron transfer, (iv) simple two-electron transfer to Cr^{VI} or its intermediate valency state. E° for Cr^{VI} - Cr^{III} couple (1.3 V) is probably not sufficient to oxidise the substrates and the reaction mixture does not turn green instantaneously to indicate the presence of Cr^{III} . Therefore, direct three-electron transfer to the bichromate or dichromate ion is not possible in the present oxida-

tion reaction. Benzilic and benzylphenylglycollic acids do not contain C—H bonds adjacent to COOH groups as mandelic acid. Since a common mechanism is envisaged for all the substrates studied, the rate determining C—H bond cleavage by two-electron process is excluded. In view of the above considerations, the oxidation of α -hydroxy acids by acid dichromate in aqueous acetic acid media may be suggested to proceed through the rapid formation of cyclic chromate ester by the interaction of α -hydroxy acid with hydrogen ion and dichromate ion. The cyclic chromate ester then breaks down in a rate determining step, by oxidative decarboxylation to form the products. The transition state leading to the decomposition of such cyclic chromate ester is stabilised by the presence of phenyl or benzyl groups in benzilic and benzylphenylglycollic acids as compared to the presence of H atom in mandelic acid and thus the rates of oxidation of benzilic and benzylphenylglycollic acid are found to be higher than mandelic acid. Lactic acid appears to be oxidised at a slower rate than mandelic acid as a CH_3 group substitution in place of phenyl group would destabilise the cyclic ester. In consideration of the above discussion, stoichiometry and product formed, the mechanism shown in Scheme 1 is suggested for the oxidation of α -hydroxy acids by acid dichromate.

Similar views have been expressed by Chang and Westheimer¹⁹ in the oxidation of pinacol by chromic acid.

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